

A Study on Visual Identity of Robotic Products — Focused on Four Classifications of Social robots

Bomi Kim - Industrial Design Department, KAIST, Daejeon, Korea, (82) 164216063, wizard-5@hanmail.net

Hyeonjeong Suk - Industrial Design Department, KAIST, Daejeon, Korea, (82) 1038185358, h.j.suk@kaist.ac.kr

Myungsuk Kim - Industrial Design Department, KAIST, Daejeon, Korea, (82) 114534511, kimmyungsuk@kaist.ac.kr

Abstract

An empirical study was carried out in order to investigate the visual identity of robot products utilizing formal factors. In particular, the four classifications of robot appearance were employed and four types of the robots were devised in each classification by varying widths of components and proportion among components. The subjects were asked to evaluate the uniformity among four robots and then the similarity between pairs of robots in each set. Based on the ratings, Multi-Dimensional Analysis was conducted and the results are summarized into three parts: First, the subjects perceived that anthropomorphic and caricatured robots are more morphologically comparable to each other. In comparison with the other three types, it is more difficult to group the functional robot; Second, a robot set which has similarity of head/screen-width is the most effective formal factor; Third, an impression of chubbiness connects robots.

Conference theme: Teaching across cultures design

Keywords: a robot classification, a body feature as the visual identity, the uniformity in a robot set

Introduction

The products surrounding us are becoming more robotized and intelligent with advances in technology by as we progress toward a 'ubiquitous environment'. In the near future, intelligent products or robotized products such as smart brushes and smart tires will become commonplace like homes: (Sung, 2008) Robotized products will support human life in a comprehensive and systematic manner. Accordingly, the identity among robotized products helps manage the products easily. In Particular, the management of identity through appearance among robotized products within the various systems which help human life can be required due to make powerful and robust brand image such as the identity of common products. Consequently, the robot product families with formal factors that represent the identities of robotized products should be built. A product family is defined as products share a common product platform including modules, core technology and design but have specific features and functionality to satisfy different sets of customers: (Meyer, Utterback, 1993)

Among the elements comprising a product family, design is the most perceivable factor for general users. In addition, the appearance of robot is an important element for in terms of the first impression made on users: (Ryu, Kwak, Kim, 2007) Breazeal (2002) addressed that the appearance of a robot as well as its way of moving and its expression delivers characteristics to the human interacting with the robot. Studies on robot appearance have dominantly focused on the head of the robot, and thus further study on robot body features is necessary. Fong (Nourbakhsh, Dautengagn, 2003) contended that the form and structure of a robot are among the factors by which a human forms expectations and stereotypes about the robot. Accordingly, the present paper deals with formal factors, particularly those among the elements comprising a product family.

The main objective of this paper is to investigate the visual identity of robot products utilizing formal factors. A questionnaire with 16 images showing varying widths of components and proportion among components was devised and evaluated by participants in the study.

Physical features of a social robot

Classification of a social robot

Robotized products can have unique appearances that diverge from the humanoid type according to their roles and levels of intelligence. Fong (2003) classified social robots according to appearance into four categories: anthropomorphic, zoomorphic, caricatured and functional. Table 1 describes the characteristics of each class.

Anthropomorphic	A tendency to attribute human characteristics including structure or function to objects with a view to helping rationalize their actions
Zoomorphic	A design to imitate living creatures. The most common designs are inspired by typical pets such as dogs and cats.
Caricatured	A character does not have to appear realistic in order to be believable.
Functional	The design of physical features is guided purely by operational objectives.

Table 1: Classification of social robots

This study employed the aforementioned four classifications that have specific features of appearance in each class.

Body features according to classification

A recent study conducted by Shin(Kwak, Kim, 2007) provided mental models of body features and quantities according to Fong’s four classification of robots into four classes (Table 2).

	head	neck	body	Leg	foot	wheel	arm	Hand	tail	screen
Anthropomorphic	1	1	1	2	2	0	2	2	0	0
Zoomorphic	1	0	1	4	2,4	0	0	0	1	0
Caricatured	1	0	1	0	0	0,2	0,2	0	0	0
Functional	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1

– Gray boxes denote a statistically significant difference ($p < 0.05$).

Table 2: Body features and quantities according to the classification

In an anthropomorphic robot, in order of importance, a head, legs (2), arms (2), feet (2), hands (2), a body, and a neck are required. A zoomorphic robot needs a head, a body, legs (4) and a tail, according to priority. A caricatured robot requires a head and body. In order of importance, a body, a screen, and wheels (2) are necessary in a functional robot.

In the study, incidental elements such as hands and feet were removed to minimize complicated elements. As a result, the anthropomorphic robot consists of a head, legs, arms, a body, and a neck, while the caricatured robot is composed of a head and a body. The zoomorphic robot has a head, a body, legs, and a tail, and the functional robot is made of a body, a screen, and wheels.

Horizontal elements as physical features

Choi (1997) suggested that width and height are important elements in the classification of a woman's body according to form factors. Ryu(2007) divided the body into horizontal elements and vertical elements to investigate body features of teaching assistant robots.

The majority of anthropomorphic robots are roughly as the height of a child owing to design goals to imitate the erect posture of a human. By contrast, the height of zoomorphic robots is considerably smaller in order to mimic creatures such as dogs. As a consequence, this study employed horizontal elements as physical features.

The robots in the four classification consisted of two components. Three classes except the functional robot are composed of a body and a head, and the functional robot is made of a body and a screen. The present study derived independent variables from the respective widths of two components and the proportion between components. The variable of width between legs or wheels was not considered owing to difficulties in perception.

Experiment

Main purpose of this study is to investigate the visual identity among a multiplicity of robot products utilizing formal factors.

The four classifications of robot appearance were employed and four types of robots were devised to fulfill each classification by varying the components-widths and proportion between components. 16 sets composed of four robot images are developed. The experiment was carried out to evaluate the uniformity among four robots and then the similarity between pairs of robots in each set. Based on the ratings, Multi-Dimensional Analysis, a conjoint analysis and descriptive statistics were conducted.

Figure 1: Research methodology overview

Participants

Thirty-two participants (17 males and 15 females) in their twenties from KAIST participated in the experiment. They were university students who adapted to new products well and majored in design.

Materials

The present study conducted an experiment with 2D images. 2D images are limited in that participants cannot perceive volume, reality, and scale. Nevertheless, subjects can direct more attention to independent variables as complicated elements are removed. Elements of components were made of standard squares to emphasize a machine-like impression and remove complex elements. In the experiment, 16 images (4x4) comprising four images for each of the four classifications are utilized (Table3).

		1	2	3	4
Images of Robots	Anthropomorphic				
	Zoomorphic				
	Caricatured				
	functional				
Conditions	Proportion	1 : 1.2	1 : 1.2	1 : 1.8	1 : 1.8
	Head/screen-width	I	II	I	II
	Body-width	A	B	B	C

Table3: Images of robots and conditions of independent variables according to types

Versions of each robot image are made on the basis of two proportions, 1 to 1.2 or 1 to 1.8. The head/screen component is composed of two type widths (I , II). For the body component, three different widths are considered. A body-width that is 1.2 times greater than the II head is consistent with a body width that is 1.8 times greater than the I head. The conditions were devised to examine whether the common feature of body-width or the common feature of proportion between components can be perceived more easily.

The number of possible sets that can be created with the 16 images is 256 (4^4). A conjoint analysis was performed to reduce the number of combinations from 256 sets to 16 sets for efficiency (Table 4).

The subjects were asked to evaluate the uniformity among four robots and then the similarity between pairs of robots in each set using a 5-point Likert scale

No	A	Z	C	F	Set Image	No	A	Z	C	F	Set Image
1	1	1	1	1		9	2	4	4	1	
2	2	2	3	4		10	1	3	2	4	
3	3	2	2	1		11	3	1	3	3	
4	3	4	1	4		12	3	3	4	2	
5	1	4	3	2		13	2	1	2	2	
6	1	2	4	3		14	4	2	1	2	
7	2	3	1	3		15	4	3	3	1	
8	4	4	2	3		16	4	1	4	4	

Table 4: Structure of 16 sets generated from the conjoint analysis

A: Anthropomorphic, Z: Zoomorphic, C: Caricatured, F: Functional

Procedure

The experiment was conducted after instruction about questionnaire and lasted about 20 minutes.

Participants measured the uniformity of 16 sets. 7 items comprised the questions of one set.

While the experiment was performed, participants could not respond to a question that they had already answered in order to provide a fixed standard for the responses.

Results

The result showed robot family-recognition according to types, components, and characteristics of width.

Robot family-recognition according to types

Robot family-recognition according to types was evaluated by a conjoint analysis (Figure 2) and MDS.

The conjoint analysis revealed that, while participants measured the uniformity of families, they were affected by zoomorphic robots and functional robots (Pearson's $R = .870$, Kendall's tau $= .706$).

Figure 2: Results of the conjoint analysis

16 sets were inspected through MDS to investigate detailed patterns. 3 sets did not show specific patterns. Anthropomorphic robots and caricatured robots were perceived similarly in 8 sets (62%) among the other 13 sets. In other words, the subjects perceive that anthropomorphic robots and caricatured robots are more morphologically comparable to each other regardless of the common features of body-width, head/screen-width, and proportion. Additionally, for 6 sets among 13 sets it was indicated that one type was difficult to group in comparison with the other three types. A functional robot was difficult to perceive as belonging to a robot family in 4 sets (66.7%) among 6 sets. In 2 sets (33.7%), a zoomorphic robot was not perceived well as belonging to a robot family.

As a result, in comparison with the other three types, it is more difficult to group the functional robot.

Figure 3: Patterns where one type is separated.

(Right pattern is $RSQ = .78440$, Left pattern is $RSQ = .62023$)

Robot family-recognition according to components

Robot family-recognition according to components was indicated through a statistical analysis (Cronbach’s alpha = 0.929). The data was analyzed case by case using the conditions of independent variables (Table 5) of set and descriptive statistics (Figure 5). Six sets including set 11, set 8, set1, set 13, set 9 and set 2 in order of high score were over the mean (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Statistical analysis of 16 sets

Set 1	Proportion	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.2
	Head/screen-width	I	I	I	I
	Body-width	A	A	A	A
Set 2	Proportion	1.2	1.8	1.2	1.8
	Head/screen-width	II	I	II	II
	Body-width	B	B	B	C
Set 3	Proportion	1.8	1.2	1.2	1.2
	Head/screen-width	I	II	II	I
	Body-width	B	B	B	A

Table 5: Examples of the conditions of independent variables

Independent variables comprising body-width, a head/screen-width and the proportion between components were compared with each other.

First, a head-width was compared with the proportion between components. In Figure 5, set 4 and set 9 have similar elements of body, but set 4 has higher commonality of proportion than set 9. In set 9, the commonality of head-width is larger than that of the proportion. The mean difference between set 4 and set 9 is 0.56, and the mean of set 9 is larger than that of set 4. The findings through the comparison of sets such as set 4 and set 9 revealed that a robot set that has similarity of head/screen-width is more effective formal factor for establishing a robot family.

Figure 5: Comparison of sets

Second, head-width was compared with body-width. Most of the results indicated that head/screen-width is more effectively perceived, but a few divergent cases also appeared. However, the cases that showed that head-width is a more effective factors than body-width had a considerably large mean difference, such as 1.22 or 0.59. In contrast, the mean difference among

divergent cases was small, such as 0.19. This reflects that head/screen-width is perceived more easily than body-width.

Third, a comparison between body-width and the proportion between components was conducted. In 75 percent of cases (3 among 4 cases), body-width was a more perceivable factor than proportion. It is thus interpreted that body-width is perceived more easily than proportion.

Robot family-recognition according to characteristics of width

Each set lends different impressions according to the variation of proportion or width. In other words, the impression of a set is explained by characteristics of width. Robot family-recognition according to the impression of the set was analyzed by using set conditions of independent variables (Table 5) and descriptive statistics (Figure 5).

The analysis was conducted according to the scale of two proportions, head/screen-width and body-width. The results showed that the larger the difference of the proportion is, the more easily participants perceived formal factor for establishing a robot family. In the results of the head-width analysis, a set that has commonality of large head-width is perceived more easily than one with a small head (3 among 4 cases). Although there is only one case that compares body-width, it is concluded that large body-width is a more effective factor for constructing a robot family than is small body-width.

Conclusion

The aim of this study was to investigate the visual identity of robot products utilizing formal factors. A questionnaire with robot images where the component-widths and proportion between components were varied was designed and presented to participants of the experiment. From the experimental results, the subjects perceived that anthropomorphic and caricatured robots are more morphologically comparable to each other. In comparison with the other three types, functional robots are less easily grouped. A robot set is perceived more effectively by head/screen-width, body-width, and proportion between components, in order. In addition, an impression of chubbiness connects robots. This study lays a foundation for future work on visual identity for constructing robot families.

Discussion

The results indicate that head-width is the most effective factor for creating a robot family. When a human meets another human for the first time, he or she receives an impression through their counterpart's face. Simultaneously, it can be argued that the head of a robot is perceived easily. Unlike a body, the head does not have incidental elements, and thus the levels of recognition can be higher than for the body.

From the results, it is found that an impression of chubbiness connects robots. An oversized feature is more perceivable than small size. In addition, an oversized body can lend a strange or unusual impression. Finally, a robot set of oversized bodies is perceived more easily as a robot family.

In this study, comparative statistical analysis with set conditions of independent variables was conducted. Although it was difficult to group functional robots, comparisons including functional robots were performed. As a result, there were some outliers, and the mean difference became smaller.

During the experiment, participants found it difficult to distinguish between robot sets where independent variables were varied. They frequently asked what the differences between the robot sets were, and they commented that robot sets were analogous to each other. For these reasons, estimates of uniformity assumed various aspects. Some participants measured low uniformity of all sets, at 1 or 2 points. The participants thought that the sets were either too similar or different. As a consequence, diverse results were obtained according to the participants' sensitivity to form.

Future work

The present study focused on physical factors among the elements of appearance comprising a product family. Further studies on robot families with different choices such as color and material are required. This study is limited in that it only addresses 2D images. Additional research with 3D images or prototypes is necessary.

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